

INNOVATIVE APPROACHES ON FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Annotation. In this article, we will examine the challenges of teaching foreign languages and how innovative solutions can be found. This includes the impact of age factors on language learners, and how to effectively teach each of them.

Key words: teaching methods, Gamification, Game-Based Learning method, Grammar-Translation Method, direct method, Suggestopedia, Story-based and interactive learning.

Annotatsiya. Bu maqolada biz xorijiy tillarni o'qitishdagi qiyinchiliklar hamda ularga qayday innovatsion yechimlar berish mumkinligini ko'rib chiqamiz. Buning ichiga yoshga doir faktorlarning til o'rganuvchilarga ta'siri va ularning har biriga tilni samarali o'rgatishning usullari kiradi

Kalit so'zlar: o'qitish usullari, Gamifikatsiya, O'yinga asoslangan ta'lim usuli, Grammatika-tarjima usuli, to'g'ridan-to'g'ri usul, Suggestopedia, Hikoyaga asoslangan va interaktiv o'rganish.

Introduction

Nowadays, as time progresses, the demand for learning foreign languages are increasing. That is why many new teaching methods and techniques are being used in this field. Teachers use creative ideas to provide effective knowledge. However, before using these techniques, the teacher must study his audience. In this article, we will consider the use of modern and effective teaching methods during the lesson, based on the abilities of students.

Age factor on learning language and effective method for each period.

Biological language learning mainly occurs between the ages of 2-12.[1] Children at this age have strong memories and a thirst for knowledge. However, another notable aspect of learners in this age range is that they cannot sit still for long periods of time. Considering all these aspects, the most effective way to teach a foreign language to children in this age range is through the Gamification or Game-Based Learning method. Using methods such as the Grammar-Translation Method will bore the child and extinguish their interest in learning the language. *Gamification* is the use of game elements in the learning process, such as competitions, challenges, and incentives. In the field of language teaching, this methodology allows educators to design dynamic and personalized lessons, transforming the learning experience into an interactive and measurable process.[2]

Older language learners, those over the age of 40, experience a gradual decline in memory and physical inactivity. In fact, learning a new language can stimulate cognitive activity, helping to slow down age-related brain changes.[3] Therefore,

when teaching this age group, the *direct method* or *suggestopedia method* should be used. In these methods, learners feel free and the emphasis is on communication.

What is suggestopedia? Suggestopedia is a teaching method that combines pedagogy, art, and psychology. Its advantage is that the learner makes the most of the information and retains it in memory. Therefore, this method is completely suitable for elderly people.

For middle-aged children, we can also teach using the *flipped classroom method*. A *flipped classroom* is structured around the idea that lecture or direct instruction is not the best use of class time. Instead students encounter information before class, freeing class time for activities that involve higher order thinking.[4] Why is this method useful? Because middle school students are able to think freely and study independently, they can effectively divide their time between homework and new topics after they have mastered the subject. This method is considered to be the one that fully meets today's requirements. This method also provides convenience for students who live far from their place of study or who cannot attend class for some reason.

As for middle-aged people, that is, people between the ages of 18 and 30, although their brains have reached their peak of development, there may be some obstacles. Teens and adults often have more developed cognitive skills, which help them learn complex grammatical structures and new vocabulary.[3] *Story-based and interactive learning* is one of the best methods for this age range. Tools like Lingo Pie or the Netflix language learning extension teach through subtitled stories and shows. The great thing about this is that you can watch interesting content and learn grammar and vocabulary in a natural way without getting bored.

Conclusion. In conclusion, if the teacher knows the methods of teaching his students, learning a language will be easier. For example, when teaching a language to young children, it is more effective to use the new gamification method. But this method is not suitable for middle-aged people. They need an easy method to apply, such as story based and interactive learning. In this way, they can master the given material at any time and place they want. Older learners benefit from more group discussions, which can help improve speaking skills and increase listening skills in a new language during live conversations. This method is called the direct method.

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